

PERSEPSI MAHASISWA TERHADAP KECERDASAN EMOSIONAL SETELAH DITERAPKAN TEKNIK *COLLABORATIVE WRITING*

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengetahui apakah penerapan teknik *collaborative writing* dapat mengembangkan kecerdasan emosional mahasiswa. Penelitian menggunakan metode deskriptif kuantitatif. Alat pengumpul data menggunakan kuesioner berdasarkan pada 5 aspek kecerdasan emosional yang mencakup *self-awareness*, *self-regulation*, *self-motivation*, *social awareness*, dan *social skills*. Teknik analisis data dilakukan dengan perhitungan persentase dari butir kuesioner, dilanjutkan dengan interpretasi dan deskripsi data dari persepsi mahasiswa terhadap kecerdasan emosional setelah teknik *collaborative writing* diterapkan. Subjek penelitian adalah mahasiswa Sekolah Tinggi Bahasa Asing Pontianak yang mengikuti kelas *Essay Writing* dan *Literary Criticism* berjumlah 43 orang dan dipilih menggunakan teknik *purposive sampling*. Berdasarkan hasil analisis data, terjadi peningkatan kecerdasan emosional mahasiswa setelah diterapkannya teknik *collaborative writing* yang ditunjukkan dengan peningkatan respons pada aspek kecerdasan emosional.

Kata Kunci: teknik *collaborative writing*; kecerdasan emosional; mahasiswa Bahasa Inggris.

Abstract

This research aimed to find out if the implementation of collaborative writing techniques could develop the emotional intelligence of students. This research used descriptive quantitative method. Data collection tools used a questionnaire based on 5 aspects of emotional intelligence which include self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, social awareness, and social skills. The data were analyzed by calculating the percentages of each questionnaire item, then continued to interpret and describe the implementation of collaborative writing technique. The subjects of this research were 43 students of Sekolah Tinggi Bahasa Asing Pontianak who enrolled in Essay Writing and Literary Criticism classes, with a total of 43 students who were selected using purposive sampling technique. The results of the data analysis indicated that there happened improvements towards the emotional intelligence after collaborative technique was implemented shown by the increase of positive responses on emotional intelligence aspects.

Keywords: *collaborative writing technique; emotional intelligence; English language students.*